

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Calò Carducci 2014	36	6	5	17	0.88 [0.74, 0.96]	0.74 [0.52, 0.90]		
Groselj-Grenc 2009	20	3	4	9	0.83 [0.63, 0.95]	0.75 [0.43, 0.95]		
Lopez Sastre 2006	50	8	11	31	0.82 [0.70, 0.91]	0.79 [0.64, 0.91]		
Pourakbari 2010	37	52	20	46	0.65 [0.51, 0.77]	0.47 [0.37, 0.57]		
Simon 2008	20	25	5	14	0.80 [0.59, 0.93]	0.36 [0.21, 0.53]		
Vazzalwar 2004	14	12	4	21	0.78 [0.52, 0.94]	0.64 [0.45, 0.80]		

PCT Cut-off	Study	Summary statistics
<2.0	Groselj-Grenc (0.28)	
	Pourabaki (0.5)	
	Simon (0.5)	SE = 0.79 (0.71; 0.85)
	Calò Carducci (0.55)	SP = 0.63 (0.48; 0.75)
	Lopez Sastre 2006 (0.59)	
	Vazzalwar 2004 (1)	